

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF PROVIDING THE BUSINESS SECTOR WITH QUALIFIED PERSONNEL.

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Abstract. This article presents the main ways of providing the business sector with qualified personnel, the reforms implemented in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship, ways of developing the business sector in our country, suggestions and recommendations regarding the improvement of qualified personnel.

Key words: Financial business, financial and medium-sized enterprises, human capital, gross domestic product, socio-economic development, human capital generator, outsourcing, outstaffing.

ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БИЗНЕС-СЕКТОРА КВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫМ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ.

Аннотация. В статье представлены основные пути обеспечения предпринимательского сектора квалифицированными кадрами, реформы, реализуемые в сфере малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства, пути развития предпринимательского сектора в нашей стране, предложения и рекомендации по повышению квалификации квалифицированных кадров.

Ключевые слова: Финансовый бизнес, финансовые и средние предприятия, человеческий капитал, валовой внутренний продукт, социально-экономическое развитие, генератор человеческого капитала, аутсорсинг, аутстаффинг.

Small business is one of the leading sectors of the economy, largely determining the rate of economic growth, regional development of the country, the state of employment of the population, the structure and quality of the gross national product. The development of small business meets global trends in the formation of a flexible mixed economy, involves a combination of different forms of ownership and an economic model adequate to them, in which a complex synthesis of a competitive market mechanism and state regulation of large, medium and small production is realized. World practice convincingly shows that even in countries with developed market economies, small businesses have a significant impact on economic development, solving social problems, and increasing the number of employed workers.

In some countries, small and medium-sized enterprises occupy a dominant position in terms of number and share in the production of goods, performance of work, and provision of services compared to large ones. It is noteworthy that the study involved scientists from five countries, such as Russia, Ukraine, Tajikistan,

China and Uzbekistan. The territory of these countries occupies about 20% of the world's landmass, the population is more than 20% of the total world population, and the total GDP is 18.2% of world GDP.¹

¹ <https://www.ilo.org/moscow/dw4sd/themes/employment-rich/lang--ru/index.htm>

Support and development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is a fundamental issue in the economic development of the republic. The importance of SMEs in modern conditions is determined by the following factors: small and medium-sized businesses create competition in the markets for goods and services, fill market niches not occupied by large businesses; small and medium-sized businesses have great potential for creating new jobs, helping to reduce unemployment and social tension; the formation and development of small and medium-sized businesses changes the social psychology and life guidelines of the population, entrepreneurs form the basis of the middle class, which acts as a guarantor of the political and social stability of the state; the development of small and medium-sized businesses contributes to the growth of tax revenues to budgets of all levels. Small and medium-sized businesses are a stabilizing factor for the economy - they are flexible and adaptable to market conditions, the ability to quickly change the structure of production, quickly create and apply new technologies and scientific developments.²

Many labor supply contests require that a certain amount of investment be made by the worker. If we call it an investment, then the worker incurs the initial costs in the hope of recouping later. Therefore, for many workers, wages and working conditions are not the only factors that are important in decision-making. To model such decisions, it is necessary to take into account the nature of the investment and the future perspective of the worker.

At present, almost all countries of the world pay attention to the development of the main component of human capital - education. 100 years ago, state spending on education was 1.0% of GDP. Currently, this indicator has reached 5.1%. As a result, the number of people with primary education in the world has exceeded 94.0% of the total population.

Spending on scientific development is also an investment in human capital. In the course of the development of science, only innovations, extremely highperformance machines and equipment are created, and based on them, not only new production technologies are formed, but also people themselves, who have new abilities and needs, change in terms of quality. In the information society, science becomes a unique "generator of human capital".

Human capital is the main wealth and the most valuable resource of any society, the main criterion of socio-economic development. The problem of studying a person, forming human capital, its general creative qualities and abilities, and investing in human capital is one of the main and central problems of world science. Therefore, it remains relevant to study the problems of the formation of human capital and its effective use in the 21st century, and to expand the possibilities of its further development. Prospects for the further social and economic development of Uzbekistan are related to the qualitative development of human creative abilities, which has become the main factor in the development of a knowledge-based economy. The human capital of the nation is one of the main components of the national wealth of the society. Therefore, it remains relevant to study the problems of effective use of accumulated human capital, to expand the possibilities of its further development, as well as to develop scientifically based recommendations on the formation and more complete implementation of human capital.

² <https://storage.strategy24.ru/files/news/202110/a4d1276db99908f68ea1559e6ec7f831.pdf>

According to existing legislation, small enterprises include enterprises whose maximum number of employees: in agriculture, forestry and fisheries is up to 50 people, in industry varies from 100 to 270 people depending on the type of activity; in trade and services – from 25 to 50 people.

The following conditions have been created in the republic for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship:

1. The time to register a small business is 30 minutes. To register a subject, as an individual entrepreneur, you need to prepare only one document, and as a small enterprise with a legal entity - two documents.

2. The single tax rate, which practically applies to all small businesses, is 5% of the volume of goods and services sold, which is an important factor in creating favorable conditions for the development of small businesses. The current rate of the single social payment, which applies to all types of activities of small businesses, is 15%.

3. Newly created production enterprises with foreign investment are given the right to apply for five years the tax rates and other obligatory payments in force on the date of their registration. Starting from 2018, small businesses owning more than 1 hectare of land pay a single land tax.

4. Financial support for small businesses is provided through: issuing loans by banks at a subsidized rate; guarantees from the State Fund for Supporting the

Development of Entrepreneurship for business entities in the amount of up to 50% of the amount of the loan received and provision by the Fund of compensation for interest expenses on loans from commercial banks.

5. Business interests are protected by the institution of the Commissioner for the Protection of the Rights and Legitimate Interests of Business Entities. In Uzbekistan, unscheduled inspections of small businesses have been cancelled, business entities that have committed financial and economic offenses for the first time are exempt from all types of liability;

6. Entrepreneurship assistance centers have been created in all regions of the country and are located in premises where unified centers operate to provide public services to business entities on the “one window” principle. Business incubators have been created for aspiring entrepreneurs, which provide legal and advisory support in preparing business plans and obtaining the necessary information.

7. Throughout the country, training courses have been organized for entrepreneurs on running a business implementing projects on the basis of privatized facilities, youth entrepreneurship clusters have been created, where young start-up entrepreneurs are provided with space to rent at a zero rate for a period of 5 years.³

³https://www.researchgate.net/profile/NozimMuminov/publication/343822220_REGULIROVANIE_DEAT_ELNOSTI_SUBEKTOV_MAL_GO_PREDPRINIMAT_ELASTVA_V_NACALE_XXI_VEKA_MIROVOJ_OPYT_Mezdunarodnaa_kollektivnaa_monografiaToms_k_Izdatel_ski_Dom_Tomskogo_gosudarstvennogo_universiteta_2020-332s-/links/5f42f41692851cd3022231f0/REGULIROVANIE-DEATELNOSTI-SUBEKTOV-MALOGO-PREDPRINIMATELSTVA-V-NACALE-XXI-VEKA-MIROVOJ-OPYT-

Based on the above, we will analyze the use of outsourcing and outsourcing services, which have achieved a number of achievements in the world experience, in order to strengthen the role of the human capital factor in business activities.

At present, when renting a production and service building requires a lot of money, transferring part of the functions in enterprises and organizations to remote work allows to save a lot of money. Employees themselves want to work at home, because it significantly reduces their expenses for meals on the way to the place of work.

Researches conducted in developed countries have shown that today mostly people with higher education and the optimal age of 26-42 are engaged in remote work. Including, if 45,0% of employees working remotely correspond to small and medium-sized businesses, it is 29,0% in large companies.

"Relationships at a distance" between employers and employees is a component of the process of decentralization of labor activity in time and space. It also serves to create a flexible virtual labor market.

The main purpose of the outstaffing service is to solve problems related to optimizing the number of personnel. Using this form of employment gives employers the following opportunities:

- optimization of personnel management for enterprises that do not have separate personnel services;
- optimization of personnel service structure of the enterprise;
- volume of enterprise accounting activities
- improvement;
- reduce the number of employees in the staff;
- neglecting one's obligations to the employer regarding social and labor relations with employees;
- ensuring the proportionality of the number of employees to the real volume of work;
- effective allocation of budget funds;
- to be free from legal obligations to employees;
- save costs for hiring an employee, paying him wages, making various social payments, preparing reports;
- not to be forced to fire their employees.

Outstaffing allows employers to regulate the number of employees while maintaining the current number of employees. In this case, companies will have the opportunity to focus all their attention on the development of their core business. Outstaffing is especially effective in optimizing the number of administrative employees and performing project work.

The following advantages of outsourcing are highlighted:

- the company can hire qualified employees for a short period of time;
- save various costs associated with short-term hiring of new employees;
- the ability to replace employees who are not satisfied with the company;

- saving costs related to employee dismissal;
- permanent employment of an acceptable employee, etc.

In conclusion, we can say that I would like to give a number of proposals and recommendations on ways to develop human capital in business.:

The wording of the provision on commercial bribery of third parties capable of influencing the transaction has been clarified. The commission of commercial bribery by employees of an economic entity is equated to the actions of the entity itself.

liability of third parties is provided for the receipt, disclosure, competition was clarified, the the concept of unfair and use of information that obviously constitutes a trade secret lists of specific types of unfair and received from employees, former employees of the victim competition were given an and other organizations or individuals. open character. provisions on false The rules on counterfeiting the specifics of combating unfair competition in the advertising have been and misrepresentation have Internet sphere have been clarified and detailed. been improved. regulated.

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